

THE ROLE OF VALUES IN ECONOMIC SLOWDOWN TIMES

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Abstract

Purpose – *This paper highlights the role of the professional values in reiterating the business units' strategy in the current pandemic times.*

Findings - *The literature studies values' role and culture in rooting the business idea, in choosing the customers, partners, suppliers, teams, business model, in the employees' lifecycle, in the organization's success or depression, in the behavior in front of the external factors, but unfortunately it is not offering a sufficient share of practical examples on managing in VUCA times.*

Practical implications – *How successful organizations handle the meltdown, looking into the global companies' approach can be interpreted in a weighted way, and the measures are a good source of inspiration for other business units.*

Value – *The paper analyzes the companies' strategic measures of adapting to the current times, with the main focus on People. What is the role of a value driven professional mindset in adapting, sometimes spontaneously, to the economic environment? If the first thought relates to having the right set up so that the employees can easily achieve excellence in functional capabilities, one must not ignore the nurturing and preservation of personal and professional values, which are the basis of one's motivation and commitment.*

Key words: *Change, Strategy, Values*

Introduction

The literature offers countless fundamental studies on the importance of the organizational culture, of the so-called company DNA that employees are sharing, or not. People's values are being lived in the working environment too and they are in fact the engine, the main drive in achieving the professional goals, along with, of course, the functional capabilities.

Day in day out, all being out and about and caught into the rush of duty, business life, success even, where the external factors leave too much place into guiding our leaders' measures, followed by the employees' actions, the professional values often remain posters hanging on the office walls, motivational notes in the printed agendas or screensavers on the desktops and unfortunately, they are not always used and perceived as they should, as driving one's professional activity.

The objective of this paper is to highlight the role of the professional values in reiterating the strategy of economic agents in the current pandemic times.

The literature is flowing with strategic models helping out companies recovering, same as there is state support in place for life after the sudden downturn. Consulting agencies are ready to offer their service on the topic, forecasting a financial boom, same as other industries and clever minds can benefit upon the current economic depression.

While the impact of the global recession stays insignificant compared to the human loss, one can see how the economic crisis is not just about the meltdown or stagnation of production, investment or services.

The negative growth of the Gross Domestic Product, the social impact created by the pandemic and economic crisis affects the population (and the unemployment rate is only one of the indicators). Certainly, the emphasis is, where possible, on maintaining the employment relations, in the view of resuming work as soon as possible.

The literature studies the role of the values and culture in rooting the business idea, in bringing it to life, in choosing the customers, partners, suppliers, teams, business model, in the employees' lifecycle, in the organization's success or depression, in the behavior in front of the external factors (political, economic, social), but unfortunately it is not offering a sufficient share of practical examples on recovering after the pandemic.

Although already convinced of the importance of a value driven mindset in the professional environment, I would not have thought that the completion of my doctoral thesis. *The implications of Human Resource Management in the Development of Family Business in Romania* will happen in the midst of a pandemic and economic crisis. Because travelling and the use of classical research methods are not possible, the paper aims to complete by accessing these main fronts: the professional, educational and life experience of the researcher and the online bibliographic sources.

Organizational Values and their Role in the People Strategy

A correct business strategy will always include a correct people strategy, in which employees are offered levers for their professional development. Just as the strategy involves measures to meet its goals in the short, medium and long term, so a good personnel strategy aims to prepare the workforce in such a way that it meets the future needs of the labor market. What is the role of a value driven professional mindset in adapting, sometimes spontaneously, to the economic environment? If the first thought relates to having the right set up so that the employees can easily achieve excellence in functional capabilities, one must not ignore the nurturing and preservation of the importance of personal and professional values, which are the basis of one's motivation and commitment.

This paper intends to embed the findings from one of the studies carried out within the doctoral thesis *The implications of Human Resource Management in the Development of Family Business in Romania* and to interpret them given the current situation. If the majority of the corporations have already defined their Mission, Vision and Values, small family businesses lack this part in the content of their website. Thus, I interviewed a sample of 12 entrepreneurs running small businesses, but with high potential, especially in the service industry and HORECA, Romania, 2018. To the question *What are the values that underlie the business?*, entrepreneurs had difficulty answering concretely. Why? Naturally, at the beginning of the road, the business idea should be immediately followed by action. Intrinsic motivation is present as an engine, without being able to be consciously assigned words and values.

I thus applied an exercise of awareness of the personal values, because they are, each time, the basis of motivation. Entrepreneurs were offered a list of values, and the exercise consisted in choosing a top of 15, 10 and then 5 values which they identify with. The interview ended with the 3 questions, in order to urge the founders to reflect. The same survey was applied on 24 employees.

Why do you think you identify yourself with the 5 chosen values?/ How do you live these values daily?/ How do you think that you can translate these values into expected behaviors at work?

Below, the values included in the survey, in an alphabetical order: adventure, authority, belonging, challenge, community, creativity, culture, dependency, efficiency, empathy, engagement, equality, freedom, friendship, health, honesty, inner harmony, innovation, integrity, job security, money, material well-being, nature, passion, politeness, prestige, professional development, professionalism, relationship, respect, respect for traditions, responsibility, returning favors, self-awareness, sense of life, social power, social recognition, spiritual life, stability, success, sustainability, teamwork, wisdom.

In the graphic below the top values of the employers are listed, followed by the employees' top and the, on the third graphic, a correlation of both groups can be easily observed.

Figure 1. Top Values Employers

Figure 2. Top Values Employees

Teamwork is the value that is in the top three for both employees and the employers. Teamwork and a good collaboration at work becomes essential, especially for a family business but not only, where without the community, could the business not exist. The synergy between the members is the source of reaching together, through a joint effort, achievements and results. The team, for employees, responds to an important social need, strongly expressed in the questionnaire by choosing values such

as quality of relationships, friendship, sense of belonging, community, in the top five of the most important values, thus this aspect cannot be subject to compromise.

Figure 3. Top Values Employees and Employers

Profit or remuneration are to be found in the top 5 selected values for the both groups. The financial aspect presents a contradiction between the interests of employees and the interests of employers. For employers it means profit, business development, and for employees it means the remuneration and benefits received for the work they perform. Job safety and health are among the top values of employees, but not in the top values of employers. A greater trust and involvement of employees in finding solutions and problem solving at the company level will increase the entrepreneurial spirit and attachment to the company's results and evolution. Increasing job satisfaction will strengthen the feeling of having job security as well as a general state of harmony, health, with a substantial reduction of the motivational sick leave. Professional development is another value that is in the top four for employees and not in the top 10 for employers. If the company does not provide career plans for its employees, especially due to economic and market conditions, I recommend granting autonomy to employees to develop their creativity and personal skills through organic and natural means. A learning organization is the ideal environment for professional development and a great method of increasing the employees' engagement.

The Role of Values in Economic Slowdown Times

We have noticed that values play a particularly important role in shaping the organizational culture and commitment in the workplace. What happens when, in unfavorable and unforeseen conditions, everyday life is marked by a global change and everything is subject to coming into question? Unfortunately, organizations do not have the capacity to be proactively prepared for all risk levels. Therefore, agile work methodology and the so called agile organizations have the chance to adapt to crisis situations and even to transform these risks from threats into opportunities, in some situations or areas of activity.

A lot of the operating business models overcame structural changes and a big amount of them decided to temporarily suspend their activity or even to suspend it. There are countries, regions, organizations that will still be able to manage more effectively, if not favorably, the adverse effects of the depression. In my study I dive deep into how successful organizations handle the meltdown, looking into the global

companies' approach. Of course, the data, the measures, the strategies cannot be the same globally, but the overall impact can be interpreted in a weighted way, and the measures are a good source of inspiration for other economic agents.

A Successful Response to the Current Situation

Without any intention of showing thankfulness for the current situation worldwide, part of coping with it means adapting to it. Care for People is and should remain top priority. How do some companies manage to succeed in VUCA (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity and Ambiguity) times? The VUCA environment takes issue in finding a customized way to the present condition. While at times, companies find themselves in challenging situations, now the entire world can be described as so. Developing an empathic behavior, being even more concerned about the People's needs would altogether put purpose and meaning in the center of attention. Most agile teams practiced such foundational agile elements before the pandemic, so they could continue their work almost seamlessly under lockdown. This is one the sort of a successful response of adapting to the current situation in which agile organizations manage to outperform. Satya Nadella's statement, Microsoft CEO, stays memorable, yet so true: "The COVID-19 pandemic has driven two years' worth of transformation in two months."

Although the VUCA concept might be considered as old, dating from 1987, it is as valid as it could be. Combining vision, understanding, clarity and agility, it offers the right mindset to counter the unwanted results of volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity, at a company, team, individual level, in a strategic approach.

- Vision – a shared vision which is worth striving for
- Understanding – for each other and listening
- Clarity – internally and externally, combined with transparency in communication
- Agility – in mindset, behavior and actions

Turning to default to transparency in uncertain situations becomes a must and creates psychological safety (or the opposite) in moments of insights, leading to connection and understanding, ultimately to having a shared feeling of meaning and purpose. This will give people a clear focus and help them to react quickly to change.

Therefore, companies should follow two main focuses: people and business. While they are interconnected, as they depend on each other, expressing clear work streams or strategies will fight ambiguity and give people a clear direction or expectation.

1. Protecting the employees by keeping them safe from harm, protecting the business unit by keeping it operational at all times, while contributing to the society goal of slowing down the spread if the virus
2. Managing impact on the business and calibrating appropriate measures to protect the financial health in the economic slowdown times

While COVID-19 surprised us all, the slowdown that followed was expected. Many companies switched to a zero-based recruitment approach and tried the most to keep their own workforce committed. At a people level (1), holding onto staff should stay a top business priority, hence ensuring business growth after the meltdown and ultimately, raising loyalty and engagement of both employees and customers. Besides the social implications, "Companies that lay off too much of their workforce and reduce headcount in their sales departments, in particular, will struggle to capture new businesses when the economy picks up. Thinking beyond the downturn is imperative." (John Wilson, WilsonHCG, 2020).

Recruitment. Unfortunately with more people looking for jobs, the number of successful candidates remained a fixed one whereas rejected applications raise at an exponential rate. More than ever, on the way to recovery, customers are important. The connection between profitability and employer branding is not any longer a secret. A study published by Careerarc shows that 65 percent of the jobseekers say that a poor candidate experience would make them less likely to purchase goods and services from that particular employer. This means that unsuccessful candidates need to have a positive experience too.

Remote working became another hot topic and suddenly companies needed to provide the necessary equipment and frame to make this new working style that once was perceived as a benefit, possible.

While co-location has often been seen as a prerequisite for the agile way of working, the pandemic has shown that agile teams can be highly effective in a remote setting. The critical success factors have been a stringent adherence to the agile cadence, efficient use of remote-collaboration tools, and the creation of a virtual co-location. Many organizations reported that being remote helped them to be virtually co-located and become more effective.

Diversity and inclusion, together with bias, stayed as important as they were before, only that the new context brought the topics to more light. Diversity and inclusion is inherently linked with innovation, strong company cultures and psychologically secure environments and teams. In an inclusive culture, belonging signals team members feel valued, respected and accepted as individuals — which helps them to participate and contribute uniquely and authentically.

Job rotation, job assignments. Temporary assignments, commonly also known as secondments, became common practices for agile organizations. Staying adaptable means also encouraging people to learn new skills, stimulate debate and embrace creativity. Besides the big learning benefit at an individual level, altogether with keeping the occupational level, secondments have the main benefits into balancing idle capacity with high business critical demands, helping other teams in urgent need to run the business, supporting agility of internal mobility, therefore increasing cross functional and transferable learning. Below, an excerpt from my own testimonial, initially published in the internal newsletter:

Taking over my current assignment did not only allow me the opportunity to adapt to the dynamics of another team, their requirements and leadership styles, but also to celebrate and learn in collaboration with my new team, while still being part of the recruitment team. A great way to learn, discover and apply new skills! While I am sincerely hoping life will soon get back to normal, I have to admit I am also longing to have the chance to implement and test the new designed solutions. This assignment was one of the best challenges I took part in so far, encouraging my development into an area I haven't really planned before. How will this impact my future work? I am also curious to see. The sky is the limit!

Figure 4. Performance self assessment of agile business units relative to nonagile units in same organisation

At a company level (2), a top work stream is managing impact on the business and calibrating appropriate measures to protect the financial health in the economic slowdown times. Keeping the

business running is not only business beneficial but also people targeted, therefore continuing to work in an agile way fitting the VUCA environment is essential. Reprioritization is the key, together with always staying in the know to anticipate threads or take advantage of the new opportunities.

An article published by a study (25 companies across seven sectors), conducted by McKinsey shows the practical impact of agile companies, equipped with methodologies and practices that ensure fast, resilient, adaptable, reactions to shock. Companies with a strong orientation towards change, especially agile ones, are given as successful examples not for exiting slowdown access, but for adapting on the fly to the unfavorable global decline. According to their self-assessments, almost all of their agile business units responded better than their nonagile units to the shocks associated with the COVID-19 pandemic by measures of customer satisfaction, employee engagement, or operational performance.

The study emphasized how the agile teams pursued their work almost seamlessly, having an assertive reaction to the shock, without mentioning important setbacks. On the other hand, transition through and after the shock for non-agile organizations represented a struggle.

Discussion and conclusions

Interested would be to have the survey described and applied in 2018 also now. I believe foreseeable changes would be noted in the area of Health, Safety, Job security, Profit/ remuneration, as these suddenly became stringent, while values like teamwork, professional development, relationships, professionalism, belonging would still continue to stay on top, as they are intrinsic values that People have. Keeping employees motivated and committed, means making sure to respond to their needs and expectations in terms of sharing these values and playing the company's values. Organizational culture, that DNA that connects people, stays the engine, the main drive in achieving the professional goals, along with, of course, the functional capabilities, even working remotely, if not especially in the absence of a co-located working environment.

The correlation of personal values with the professional ones is possible and natural, as seen in the table below as well as the harmony between meeting the daily needs, aspirations or goals at work and outside of it, combined with the purpose of the organization. A good match between the two areas is highly beneficial for both the company and the employees.

Table 1. Harmony between the interests of the organization and the individual ones

Conditions for staying competitive	People's inner needs
Learning	Learning and exploring
Agility	Experimentation
Creativity and innovation	Creativity and innovation
Partnership	Relationship
Continuous learning	Discovering
Teamwork	People connection
Dialogue	Communication
Participation	Involvement
Risk taking	Permission to err
Proactivity	Empowerment
Informal assessment/ feedback	Solidarity and friendship
Mentoring	Closeness
Vision	Purpose
Context	Complexity and depth
Alternative roles	Experience
Inventions	Possibilities
Imagination	Reflection
Communication	Communication
Integration	Accomplishment
Expansion	Widening the horizon
People development	Growth
Common self-awareness	Attachment
Team	Community
Interest representation	Family

As stated earlier, as the strategy involves measures to meet its goals in the short, medium and long term, a good personnel strategy aims to prepare the workforce in such a way that it meets the future needs of the labor market, and this stays relevant in all times. Ensuring a good combination of team and company elements would lead to a more transparent approach, which is expected especially in uncertain situations, as feeling a shared meaning and purpose creates psychological safety (or the opposite).

References

Axelos, Global Best Practice

2018

Erfolgreiche Projekte managen mit PRINCE2

Dweck, C.

2016

Mindset: The New Psychology of Success, Ballantine Books Trade Paperback Edition

Pink, D.

2009

Drive. The Surprising Truth about What Motivates Us, Canongate Books in 2011

<https://www.gartner.com/en/marketing/insights/articles/cut-costs-not-people-7-cost-optimization-questions-for-marketers> 29.06.2020

<https://www.gartner.com/smarterwithgartner/maintain-diversity-and-inclusion-during-pandemics>
28.06.2020

https://www.mindtools.com/amember/plugins/protect/new_rewrite/login.php?v=-any&url=/community/%3froute= 17.04.2020

[https://www.vuca-world.org/#:~:text=VUCA%20is%20an%20acronym%20\(artificial,%2C%20Uncertainty%2C%20Complexity%20and%20Ambiguity.,](https://www.vuca-world.org/#:~:text=VUCA%20is%20an%20acronym%20(artificial,%2C%20Uncertainty%2C%20Complexity%20and%20Ambiguity.,) 28.06.2020

<https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/coronavirus-leading-through-the-crisis> 27.06.2020

<https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/organization/our-insights/an-operating-model-for-the-next-normal-lessons-from-agile-organizations-in-the-crisis> 27.06.2020

<https://blogs.imf.org/2020/04/06/an-early-view-of-the-economic-impact-of-the-pandemic-in-5-charts/#post/0> 27.06.2020

<https://www.lewiscotter.com/brands>, 28.06.2020

<http://www.careerarc.com/blog/2017/04/future-of-recruiting-infographic/> 30.06.2020

<http://www.scrum.org>, 28.06.2020